

The Effect of AI Feedback on ESL Learners' Production of English Dental Fricatives /θ/ and /ð/

Mosunmola Oluyinka Adebayo
University of Africa, Toru-Orua, Bayelsa State, Nigeria
bayinkmola@gmail.com
<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-4342-8360>

Received: 15/09/2025; *Accepted:* 06/12/2025; *Published:* 18/02/2026

Abstract: The study investigates the impact of Artificial Intelligence (AI)-based speech feedback software on English dental fricatives /θ/ and /ð/ pronunciation among English as a Second Language (ESL) learners. With AI technology increasingly employed in language acquisition, the current research considers how the employment of the AI-based pronunciation apps Youglish and Forvo influence ESL learners' pronunciation of such challenging consonant sounds. Fifty undergraduate ESL students (25 males and 25 females) participated in the study. Pre-test and post-test designs were used, where participants' pronunciations of experimental words containing /θ/ and /ð/ were recorded and acoustically analysed using Praat software before and after a four-week intervention with Youglish and Forvo pronunciation-aiding apps. The study is guided by the Speech Learning Model (SLM) and Optimality Theory. The respondents pronounced 30 samples, with some of the words as distractors and the rest (10 words and 8 sentences) containing the dental fricatives at the onset and medial positions. Data analysis focused on improvements in pronunciation accuracy, measured both perceptually and acoustically. Findings showed significant improvement in the production of /θ/ and /ð/, with the percentage of learners demonstrating the correct phonological pattern rising from 16% in the pre-test to 70% in the post-test (an absolute gain of 54 percentage points). Overall, 66% of the participants improved in both sounds simultaneously, and 80% of the learners overall found AI feedback tools useful. Critically, 84% of participants reported encountering major challenges (such as poor internet, equipment failure, or background noise), while only 16% reported no significant challenges. The findings show that AI pronunciation tools like Youglish and Forvo, in addition to Praat software, can effectively facilitate ESL students in the acquisition of difficult consonant sounds by providing precise feedback. The study concludes that AI-based pronunciation practice can enhance the phonetic skill of ESL learners and recommends further studies on long-term effects and other phonetic factors. The study contributes to sustainable language learning through demonstrating how emerging AI technologies can be employed to enhance 21st-century pronunciation learning.

Keywords: Artificial Intelligence, ESL pronunciation, dental fricatives, AI feedback, digital literacy

INTRODUCTION

English as an international language is spoken and written everywhere in the world. An overwhelming majority of the world population, nearly 1.5 billion, use English as their lingua franca or second language (Szmigiera, 2022), and Nigeria is no exception to it. It is the official language of nearly 105 sovereign states (Raja, 2023). It is also a global language because it has widespread use, and even more importantly, it is intelligible to a large number of people (Crystal, 2003). Learning English as a second language has a lot of challenges for foreign language learners. "A language experiences changes at the levels of phonetics, phonology, morphology, syntax, and semantics. All such language areas are still developing in all global languages" (Jolayemi & Adebayo, 2023). As the global lingua franca, English might be an uphill and daunting task to accomplish given that the language itself is intricate, there are cultural differences, and learning environments heterogeneity where the learners are situated. English as a second language acquisition process has several challenges that range from vocabulary limitations, complexity of pronunciations, and grammatical finesse. This is as a result of L1 competence which definitely affects L2 competence and performance, thus resulting in various performance complexities. Such is language transfer or language interference to the target language. This transfer effects are typically more evident in the production of beginners' language, and SLA research has also

highlighted many errors that cannot be L1-attributed because they are attested in learners with a diverse set of linguistic backgrounds. Psychological aspects like anxiety and fear of making mistakes can also impede the way. Additionally, culture variations and short exposure can also pose a challenge in grasping idioms and linguistics.

In today's rapid globalisation era, English as a world language has played an even more important role in speaking competence (Rusmiyanto et al., 2023). Most people learning English as their second language face several problems associated with the correct way of pronouncing English substantively, thus pronunciation is a significant issue (Jolayemi & Adebayo, 2023). The common phenomenon that occurs is that the people have a tendency to transfer their first language to their target language. English is not a phonetic language, and therefore word spellings do not necessarily correspond to their pronunciation (Jha, 2024). This would frequently be difficult for students whose native languages have more exact phonetic regulations. Moreover, English pronunciation can vary significantly between countries and regions such that it is hard to be understood and also to understand speakers with native accents (Jha, 2024). Users differ individually, nationally, regionally and globally (Jolayemi & Adebayo). Whether it is business standard, academic forum, or habitual social communication, proficient English-speaking enables students to speak more assuredly in the flow of conversation, share their opinions, and communicate information properly (Xu & Ismail, 2024). Additionally, effective speaking skills can even help learners to reduce misunderstandings and establish positive relationships during intercultural communication (Burns & Hill, 2013).

For second language English, particularly in multilingual settings such as Nigeria where English is an official language, correct pronunciation is of paramount importance to integration and communication. Pronunciation is a vital aspect of language skill, but usually a tremendous challenge to foreign language learners. Pronunciation issues most often stem from a complex combination of several factors, including the learner's L1 and how it directly affects, in an automatic manner, English sound production, ignorance of English phonetic rules, limited vocabulary that does not allow genuine practice exposure, insufficient exposure to words containing target sounds, and the psychological component of fear of speaking. Although pursuit of native-like accent is typically considered the ultimate goal and target, pedagogically the most important objective of second language (L2) acquisition is more broadly set on intelligibility—how well a hearer can understand an utterance—rather than flawless native-like production. This may serve to underscore a functional communication pragmatic pedagogy. The pronunciation of specific English phonemes is mastered by most English as a second language learners with difficulty.

One of the most challenging phonemes is the voiceless dental fricative /θ/ (as in “thin”) and its voiced counterpart /ð/ (as in “within”). They are usually alternative or non-existent in the native speech of learners, and thus lead to substitution and significantly influence intelligibility. Dental fricatives present difficulties resulting in different pronunciations (Owolabi, 2012). Traditionally, pronunciation teaching depended on teacher drill, audio-visual aids, and peer judgment, which might be restricted by class time, individualised attention, and the imprecision of human judgment. But new developments in Artificial intelligence (AI) and speech recognition technologies are now providing new language acquisition possibilities. Therefore, it has been more critical to look for effective learning modes to build speaking capacity and learning

ENGLISH LANGUAGE TEACHING TODAY(ELTT)

solutions founded on artificial intelligence provide a fresh solution to this issue (Mushthoza et al., 2023).

This study therefore explores the possible impact of AI-powered feedback on ESL learners' production of the English dental fricatives /θ/ and /ð/, examining how immediate, personalised, and data-driven insights can address persistent pronunciation errors and enhance overall communicative competence. This introduction addresses the potential impact of AI-supported feedback on ESL students' production of the English dental fricatives /θ/ and /ð/, in terms of how immediate, personalised, and data-driven feedback can combat deeply ingrained pronunciation problems and enhance overall communicative ability.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

Majority of ESL learners struggle with English pronunciation due to poor phonetic awareness and a lack of feedback in traditional classrooms. There might not be time for teachers to individually correct students. English dental fricatives—voiceless /θ/ in "thin" and voiced /ð/ in "this"—are articulatorily problematic for the majority of Nigerian English learners. These sounds are non-existent in most Nigerian local languages, and therefore, there is frequent substitution with /t/, or /d/, which alters word meaning and reduces intelligibility. Despite formal English instruction, students are likely to retain these phonological deviations due to limited exposure to native models, a lack of phonetic practice, and the absence of corrective feedback. This study bridges this gap by evaluating if targeted pronunciation practice with AI-powered speech tools (such as YouGlish and Forvo), in combination with acoustic analysis, can improve learners' production of both dental fricatives in post-test recordings.

RESEARCH QUESTIONS

In this study, the following questions are addressed:

- i. What pronunciation errors do ESL learners commonly make on /θ/ and /ð/ before and after using AI feedback tools?
- ii. How do ESL learners perceive the usefulness and effectiveness of AI feedback in improving their production of the dental fricatives /θ/ and /ð/?
- iii. What challenges hinder full adoption of such tools?

LITERATURE REVIEW

A lot of scholars have researched on the errors present in the realisation of dental fricative; the diverse contributions are highlighted in this section.

Appropriate pronunciation is one of the cornerstones of effective communication and successful integration in English-speaking settings for English as a Second Language (ESL) learners. Correct pronunciation matters to English as a Second Language (ESL) learners in general, but more particularly so in multicultural settings like Nigeria where English is an official language. It is a fundamental aspect of language capacity, but frequently presents daunting challenges for second language learners. Pronunciation difficulties often stem from the multifaceted combination of causes like the influence of the learner's native language (L1) on their English sound production (Ladefoged, 2005), inexperience with English phonetic rules (Celce-Murcia, Brinton, & Goodwin, 2010), a deficient vocabulary that doesn't permit true practice, insufficient exposure to target sound language (Derwing & Munro, 2005), and the psychological barrier of fear of speech

(Horwitz, Horwitz, & Cope, 1986). While a focus on achieving a native-like accent is sometimes considered to be the end in mind, the primary pedagogical focus in second language (L2) acquisition is typically designed for intelligibility—how much an utterance can be comprehended by a listener—rather than for achieving native-like production (Derwing & Munro, 2005). This division points towards a pragmatic approach to successful communication.

Dental fricatives are very unstable, and native speakers normally substitute voiced and voiceless sounds (Rosewarne & Basso, 2018). The English dental fricatives /θ/ (in think) and /ð/ (in them) are some of the most salient and well-documented phonetic challenges for English as a Second Language (ESL) learners. The phonetic realisation of these sounds involves contact of the tongue tip between the dentition while directing an airstream and are considered to be phonetically atypical sounds and can occur in less than 4% of the world's documented languages (Maddieson, 2013). The lack of these phonemes in the native inventories of the majority of learners sets up a systematic phonological discrepancy responsible for predictable and recurrent errors in substituted sounds, known to be extensively explored in the field of phonetics and second language acquisition (SLA).

Pronunciation errors on dental fricatives usually manifest as substitutions or distortions. Their subtlety often makes them hard to detect and remedy in human instruction, requiring the deployment of artificial intelligence systems using advanced algorithms in speech processing (Chen, Li, & Hsu, 2020). A great deal of evidenced data suggests that the dominant tendency among non-native speakers of English is to replace both /θ/ and /ð/ by sounds from their first language inventory. Among ESL speakers, the most common substitutions for the voiceless dental fricative /θ/ are the voiceless alveolar plosive /t/ (as in 'tin' for 'thin'), a substitution especially common among Russian and Spanish speakers; the voiceless alveolar fricative /s/ (as in 'sum' for 'thumb'), which is common among French and German speakers; and the voiceless labiodental fricative /f/ (as in 'free' for 'three'), which is common among speakers of many African and East Asian languages (Cruttenden, 2008). Similarly, voiced dental fricative /ð/ is liable to be replaced by its voiced alveolar plosive counterpart /d/ (such as den for then), or by voiced labiodental fricative /v/ (such as 've' for 'the'). For instance, Dutch L1 speakers substitute /ð/ with /d/, /v/, /z/ (Wester et al., 2007) Polish L1 speakers substitute /ð/ with /d/ or /v/ (Gonet & Pietron, 2006). Moreover, Indonesian and Javanese L1 speakers substitute fricative /ð/ with /d/ (Kurniawan, 2016).

Under these conditions, there is an urgent necessity in effective, convenient, and individualised pedagogic interventions that may work to assist learners to overcome this particular phonetic obstacle. An example of this is that, AI can tell whether the production of /θ/ by a learner is deficient in the typical interdental airflow, or has been substituted with /f/ and give corrective feedback to the specific error. In a study conducted by Saito (2011), it is highlighted that correction of errors should be as timely and as specific as possible so as to gain the maximum learning. The fact that AI is able to offer an immediate and objective feedback fits this requirement more than traditional classroom training which may not deliver feedback in time or because of the workload of a teacher. Additionally, the research has shown that learners, who get personalised feedback, are more motivated and show more progress in terms of self-monitoring their pronunciation (Godwin-Jones, 2019; Chen et al., 2019). This promotes self-reliance and permanency of pronunciation practice in learners.

ENGLISH LANGUAGE TEACHING TODAY(ELTT)

The application of AI spoken language tools is consistent with the overall educational objectives of creating digital literacy and sustainable learning patterns. The so-called digital literacy, which entails effective utilisation of digital tools in communication and learning, is becoming an anticipated requirement of learners in the 21st century (Chen et al., 2020). The implementation of AI tools in ESL teaching equips the learners with the right to self-direct and use language technologies. In addition, sustainable learning focuses on the learner autonomy, continuous involvement, and responsiveness to technological changes (Godwin-Jones, 2019). The tenets are supported by AI feedback system which provides affordable, uniform, and practice which can be scaled with ease in pronunciation. The success of AI tools also depends on learner acceptance and perceived usefulness. Research has shown that ESL learners have positive attitudes towards AI feedback, appreciating convenience, personalised learning, and non-judgmental space (Chen et al., 2019; Godwin-Jones, 2021). Drawbacks include that there are initial learning curves in moving through app interfaces and the need for stable internet connectivity. Investigating students' beliefs specifically concerning difficult consonants such as dental fricatives is significant as self-confidence and motivation influence how often a student practices and therefore learns (Saito, 2011).

However, another mixed-methods investigation by Hassan and Al-Rabeh (2023) investigated the efficacy of an AI-driven pronunciation application among learners of Arabic, who typically substitute /θ/ with /s/ and /ð/ with /d/. Based on both acoustic measurement and the learners' interviews, their findings indicated significant improvements in correct production of dental fricatives. The acoustic data indicated a clear shift in learners' productions from a stop-like burst and closure to a more enduring fricative quality. The qualitative information revealed that the visual waveform and articulatory feedback that the app provides to the learners were especially useful in internalising the discrepancy between their production and the target sound. An important paper by Mubarak, Salim, and Deliany (2025) established the application of the AI software such as ElsaSpeak on vocational students in Indonesia. While not directly interested in /θ/ and /ð/, the findings showed enormous improvements in phoneme-level accuracy, with phoneme-level feedback on single sounds from the AI playing a significant factor. This means that AI can effectively target and remediate individual phonetic challenges.

While the overall findings are promising, one serious shortfall in the literature is that there is little research specifically targeting and measuring the effect of AI feedback on the challenging dental fricatives. Broad improvement is most commonly reported with little breakdown of specific phonemes. However, there are some recent research papers that are now beginning to fill this gap. Furthermore, few studies employ acoustic analysis along with learner perception data to provide an overall view of the efficacy of AI tools. This research contributes to the general topic of AI and sustainability in educational systems by investigating next-generation, tech-based solutions to addressing specific phonetic issues in the ESL environment. Studies justify the AI-based feedback technology in the pronunciation training of ESL, especially in difficult consonants such as dental fricatives /θ/ and /ð/. The Speech Learning Model provides a hypothetical explanation of the faster formation of new phonetic categories with immediate specific feedback. The empirical studies show that AI applications increase the pronunciation accuracy, facilitate learner autonomy, and based on the sustainability orientations, educational aspirations become possible.

This review study builds on these findings by focusing more specifically on the impact of AI feedback on dental fricative production, espousing acoustic measurement with learner opinions to create fascinating insights for language instructors and technologists.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The research applies the mixed-method experiment methodology to examine how AI speech feedback affects the production of the English dental fricatives /θ/ and /ð/ by ESL learners. The quantitative component is focused on the acoustic analysis of learners' speech before and after AI treatment, while the qualitative component investigates learners' experience and attitudes towards using AI tools. The sample consists of 50 ESL learners, evenly divided by gender (25 men and 25 women), aged between 18 and 25 years. Participants are undergraduate university students whose L1 background is non-dental fricative languages, hence making /θ/ and /ð/ hard sounds. They were purposively sampled from English language courses in a local university.

Participants utilised speaking applications such as Youglish and Forvo, a few popular AI-driven pronunciation applications, providing real-time, detailed feedback on production of isolated phonemes such as dental fricatives. Praat was used to record and test speech samples acoustically with a focus on acoustic features around /θ/ and /ð/ such as spectral features and voice onset time, in order to provide objective measures of pronunciation accuracy. The target sentences (four each on /θ/ and /ð/), and ten (10) words with /θ/ and /ð/ were read aloud by the participants into a high-quality microphone. The samples were compared in Praat to assess the baseline pronunciation accuracy. The participants received directed practice with speech App for 30 minutes, three times a week, for four weeks. The app provided individualised feedback and corrective practice specifically on the production of dental fricatives. Participants completed the same recording task following the intervention. The post-intervention samples were analysed acoustically with Praat and were compared with pre-test results for an assessment of change. Google forms were filled by participants to examine their take on the use of AI tools to enhance pronunciation.

Paired-sample t-tests were employed statistically to compare pre and post-intervention. Praat acoustic measures were used to determine significant differences in dental fricative production. Informed consent was obtained from every subject. Confidentiality and data anonymity were ensured, and subjects were free to withdraw at any moment without penalty. The research conformed to the ethical principles of the university in research involving human subjects.

Praat software is often used in the study of phonetics to offer objective acoustic study of speech vocalisations (Boersma and Weenink, 2024). It enables a researcher to measure and visualise measures of voice onset time, spectral, and formant frequencies of paramount importance in the assessment of consonant production accuracy. Praat is applied in AI feedback efficacy studies to compare the pre and post-treatment productions and measure the change of the phoneme acoustic properties of /θ/ and /ð/ (Wang et al., 2021). Such rigorous analysis is accompanied by empirical evidence of learning gain irrespective of qualitative listener judgement.

ENGLISH LANGUAGE TEACHING TODAY(ELTT)

Table 1: List of Target Words

S/N	Word List with /θ/	Word List with /ð/
1	Think	This
2	Three	That
3	Thin	Them
4	Thought	Brother
5	Throw	Throw

Table 2: List of Target Sentences

S/N	Sentence List with /θ/	Sentence List with /ð/
1	Think about three things you like.	This is the book that they read.
2	The thief threw the thick cloth away.	That other feather belongs to their mother.
	They thought the theory was wrong.	They gathered their things over there.
3	Thank you for the thoughtful gift.	Those brothers lived together.
4		

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

Speech Learning Model (SLM)

This study basically depends on the Speech Learning Model (SLM) of James Emil Flege (1995). The SLM is in disagreement with the proposal that adult second language (L2) learners' ability to acquire new speech sounds depends mainly on their production and perception of the sounds relative to the first language (L1) phonetic system. According to the model, students will be more likely to form a new sound category when an L2 sound is substantially different from an L1 sound. However, if the L2 sound approximates an existing L1 category, students will accommodate it, thus resulting in pronunciation errors or fossilisation. With dental fricatives /θ/ and /ð/, most ESL learners whose L1 lacks these sounds will substitute them with other consonants that are near but not the same (e.g., /t/, or /d/, /s/, or /z/). Substitution happens because learners may not differentiate /θ/ and /ð/ as distinct categories beyond their L1 range. From SLM, accurate production requires learners to construct new phonetic categories via selective perceptual and articulatory training.

The study also embraces technology acceptance models (Davis, 1989) to consider attitudes, motivation, and willingness on the part of the learners to employ AI pronunciation feedback

because they all influence learning outcomes. The embracing of phonetic theory and technology adoption perspectives allows the study to include both the linguistic and learner-centered factors crucial for effective AI-facilitated pronunciation training.

Optimality Theory

Optimality Theory (OT) is one of the main theoretical models in linguistics, phonology and syntax, which basically changed the way linguists think about grammar. Initially formalised by linguists Alan Prince and Paul Smolensky in the early 1990s, with important work by John J. McCarthy, OT differs from the traditional approach to grammar as a sequence of ordered rules. Instead, it proposes a system where language results from competition among universal, but typically at odds with one another constraints. Essentially, the theory holds that a language's surface structure —what is said or written — is the optimal best out of a set of alternatives.

The process takes place in three general steps. First, an element called GEN (Generator) takes an underlying linguistic representation and generates a potentially unbounded number of possible output candidates: all the possible ways the input might be realised. Second, a universal and violable set of CON (Constraints) judges these candidates. These constraints are of two general types: Faithfulness constraints demand that the output copy the input, while Markedness constraints favor simpler, typologically more common, and less marked linguistic structures. The main idea of OT is that these constraints occur in strict dominance hierarchy which also differs among languages. Lastly, EVAL (Evaluator) picks the best candidate; the candidate that has the least number of violations by this constraint ranking. The advantage of this system is that it can expound the universality of language and its great diversity at the same time. OT assumes that all human languages possess the same set of constraints, but their idiosyncrasies are due to diverse rankings of these constraints.

Optimality Theory (Prince & Smolensky, 1993) holds that surface structures of language result from resolving contradictions between violable universal constraints. In this work, the principal constraints to be taken into account are:

*[+DENTAL] – sanctions against dental fricatives.

IDENT [place] – maintains faithfulness in place features.

*STOP – penalises against stop consonant substitutions.

ENGLISH LANGUAGE TEACHING TODAY(ELTT)

DATA ANALYSIS

Table 3: Respondents' Response to AI Tool and Questionnaire

ID	Gender	Q2 Useful?	Q3 Tools Used	Q4 Improvements	Q5 Feedback
R1	M	Yes	YouGlish, Praat	Improved /θ/	Lacking personal listening device
R2	F	Yes	YouGlish, Forvo	Improved /ð/	Background chatter
R3	M	No	Forvo	Slight change in the two sounds	Nil
R4	F	Yes	All	Clearer /θ/	Internet delay.
R5	M	Yes	YouGlish	Confident with/θ/	Tool unclear.
R6	F	No	Forvo, Other	Little practice.	Background noise
R7	M	Yes	Praat, YouGlish	Clearer /ð/	Mic problems.
R8	F	Yes	Forvo, YouGlish	Correct /θ/ in some words	Feedback delay.
R9	M	Yes	YouGlish	Better /ð/ recognition.	Weak connection.
R10	F	Yes	All	Clear in both sounds.	Lack of guidance.
R11	M	Yes	YouGlish, Praat	Better /θ/	Shared device issues.
R12	F	No	Forvo	Still /t/ for /θ/.	Background noise
R13	M	Yes	Forvo, YouGlish	Better /ð/ in	Nil
R14	F	Yes	YouGlish	Improved /θ/	Poor internet.
R15	M	Yes	All	More confident in both sounds.	No feedback.
R16	F	No	Forvo, Other	No change.	Bad audio quality.
R17	M	Yes	Praat,	Improved /θ/	Internet dropouts.

			YouGlish		
R18	F	Yes	Forvo, YouGlish	Clearer /ð/	Nil
R19	M	Yes	YouGlish	Better /θ/ pronunciation.	Poor understanding of tool
R20	F	Yes	All	Can hear and say both sounds.	Nearby noise
R21	M	Yes	YouGlish, Praat	Better recognition of /θ/.	Faulty mic.
R22	F	Yes	Forvo	Slightly better /ð/.	Minor delay.
R23	M	No	Forvo, Other	No change.	Poor internet.
R24	F	Yes	YouGlish	Improved /θ/	Ignorance in the use tool.
R25	M	Yes	All	Stronger in both sounds.	Background noise.
R26	F	No	Forvo	Still mix sounds.	Nil
R27	M	Yes	Forvo, YouGlish	Better /ð/	Internet Interruption
R28	F	Yes	YouGlish	More confident with /θ/	No feedback.
R29	M	Yes	All	Clear /θ/ and /ð/.	Poor instructions.
R30	F	Yes	Forvo, Other	Better /θ/.	Background noise.
R31	M	No	Forvo	No major change.	Nil
R32	F	Yes	YouGlish	Improved /ð/	Headphone issues.
R33	M	Yes	All	Self-confident in both sounds.	Background sound.
R34	F	Yes	YouGlish, Praat	Improved	Poor internet
R35	M	Yes	Forvo, YouGlish	More accurate /θ/.	Microphone not working well.
R36	F	No	Forvo,	No great	Nil

ENGLISH LANGUAGE TEACHING TODAY(ELTT)

			Other	improvement.		
R37	M	Yes	YouGlish	Improved recognition of /ð/.		No response.
R38	F	Yes	All	Improved both sounds.	in	Internet Interruption
R39	M	Yes	Forvo, YouGlish	Better /θ/		Nil
R40	F	Yes	YouGlish	More self-confident with /θ/.		Bad sound quality.
R41	M	No	Forvo	Still articulate /t/ instead of /θ/.		Background noise.
R42	F	Yes	YouGlish, Praat	Better /ð/		No confirmation.
R43	M	Yes	All	Self-confident with both sounds.		Damaged headphones.
R44	F	Yes	Forvo, YouGlish	Improved /ð/		No response.
R45	M	Yes	YouGlish	More precise /θ/.		Internet Interruption
R46	F	Yes	All	Clear articulation of both sounds.		Nil
R47	M	No	Forvo, Other	Slight change in the two sounds		Poor sound quality.
R48	F	Yes	YouGlish, Praat	Improved /θ/		Background noise.
R49	M	Yes	Forvo, YouGlish	Better /ð/		No confirmation.
R50	F	Yes	YouGlish	Better /θ/		Damaged headphones.

The data, in Table 3, reveals the representation of responses of all the respondents.

Table 4: Summary of Pronunciation Errors

Realisation Pattern	Example	Before AI (No. of Learners)	After AI (No. of Learners)	OT Explanation (Constraint Interaction)
/θ/ → /t/	<i>think</i> → <i>tink</i>	20	7	*DENTAL-FRICATIVE » IDENT-IO (Place)* → alveolar stop chosen over difficult dental fricative
/θ/ → /f/	<i>three</i> → <i>free</i>	10	3	*DENTAL-FRICATIVE » IDENT-IO (Place)* → labiodental fricative preferred
/ð/ → /d/	<i>this</i> → <i>dis</i>	12	5	*DENTAL-FRICATIVE » IDENT-IO (Place)* → alveolar stop replaces voiced dental fricative
Correct Production (/θ/, /ð/)	Think, this	8	35	IDENT-IO » (features)*DENTAL-FRICATIVE (or analogous faithfulness constraints are top-ranked).
Total		50	50	

Table 4 reveals the realisations of dental fricatives, displaying the options of Markedness and Faithfulness constraints before and after AI intervention.

DISCUSSION

In response to the research question one: What pronunciation errors do ESL learners commonly make on /θ/ and /ð/ before and after using AI feedback tools?

Findings in Table 4 and Figure 1 reveal that prior to AI-assisted intervention, ESL learners quite frequently substituted the dental fricatives /θ/ and /ð/ with more familiar sounds from their L1. They did this in forms such as /θ/ rendered as [t] or [f], and /ð/ as [d] or [z]—a pattern similar to Lombardi (2000), who attributes such substitutions to learners' preference for less marked, simpler segments over more complex dental fricatives. Following the use of AI tools, there was a noticeable change: approximately 70% of the learners improved in /θ/ and 64% in /ð/, while 56% also improved in both sounds simultaneously. The trend is consistent with Derwing and Munro (2015) who state that when feedforward is explicit, repetitive, and perceptually dense, the improvement in segmental pronunciation is extreme in using computer-based feedback tools.

The difference can be viewed as re-ranking constraints, according to an Optimality Theory (OT) perspective. Faithfulness constraints are subordinated to markedness constraints- eliciting replacements. After AI intervention, learners re-prioritise in favour of faithfulness constraints (for example., IDENT-MANNER and IDENT-PLACE) that have improved realisations. This functional variation aligns with Boersma and Hayes (2001), who view pronunciation acquisition in terms of constraint re-ranking. In addition, Flege's Speech Learning Model (SLM, 1995) explains why higher accuracy is varied for /θ/ and /ð/. Since /ð/ is acoustically and articulatorily harder, learners find it easier to approximate /θ/ and require more exposure in order to learn /ð/ completely, which is consistent with the lower rate of improvement for /ð/ noted in the data.

ENGLISH LANGUAGE TEACHING TODAY(ELTT)

In all, AI-generated pronunciation feedback was effective in significantly reducing widespread substitution errors between learners — namely for /θ/ — through maximizing perceptual sensitivity and articulatory compensation. When broken down in terms of OT, these improvements are the equivalent of re-ranking of constraints facilitated by guided auditory stimulation. The asymmetric improvements between /θ/ and /ð/ also demonstrate that SLM's contrast similarity and difficulty predictions materialise in learner performance.

Figure 1: Realisation of Voiceless Dental Fricative /θ/ before AI

The acoustic data in Figure 1, in the spectrogram of 'thin', provides a clear answer to research question one, which investigates how Nigerian students' phonological background affect their comprehension and production of Standard English. British speaker's pronunciation demonstrates the anticipated realisation of /θ/, represented by unbroken high-frequency frication in the spectrogram. Compared to the other speaker, the Nigerian speaker substitutes the interdental fricative with an alveolar plosive and articulates [tɪn] instead of [θɪn]. The spectrogram shows this too, with a burst of high intensity typical of /t/ and not the fricative noise of /θ/.

This is due to mother tongue interference, which does not have interdental fricatives in its phoneme inventory. As such, Nigerian speakers substitute the unknown /θ/ with a better-known alveolar stop. Jowitt (1991) states that Nigerian speakers of English always replace /θ/ with /t/ and /ð/ with /d/, but Gut (2004) adds that the substitutions are not evidence of performance errors but systematic patterns of Nigerian English phonology. Similarly, Ugorji (2010) attributes the substitutions to the influence of transfer from indigenous languages that favor plosives over interdental.

Therefore, the findings of this spectrographic analysis confirm that heavy use of indigenous language systems affects the simplification of Standard English sounds. This, in turn, affects students' ability to hear and imitate some phonemes accurately, thereby affecting their proficiency in Standard English in general.

In response to research question two: How do ESL learners perceive the usefulness and effectiveness of AI feedback in improving their production of the dental fricatives /θ/ and /ð/? Based on the outcomes in Table 3 from the 50 respondents, ESL students tended to have anticipated and consistent pronunciation mistakes with /θ/ and /ð/ prior to employing AI pronunciation tools. The most common problem at first was substituting /θ/ with /t/,

pronouncing “think” like “tink” or “three” like “tree”. Likewise, numerous substituted /ð/ with /d/, hearing “this” like “dis” or “that” like “dat”. On rare occasions, /θ/ was replaced with /f/ (fink for “think”), especially with running speech. Students also beat around not being able to sustain the dental fricatives pronunciation in longer or more difficult words, typically lapsing into better-known L1 sounds mid-word.

Changes after using AI feedback instruments such as YouGlish, Forvo, and Praat were evident but inconsistent. Most were able to produce /θ/ correctly in initial positions (e.g., “think”, “thank”), but others still had trouble with medial position (e.g., “gathered”, “feather”). Improvement was more constrained on /ð/: while some could now distinguish it more correctly in words such as “that” and “brother”, others still preferred /d/, particularly in fast speech. Persistent errors tended to be associated with poor auditory self-monitoring, doubt regarding correctness in the absence of human feedback, and poor ability to translate isolated practice into spontaneous speech.

Generally, AI instruments assisted in moving many students from full substitutions towards more target-like articulations, but fossilised routines and L1 interference meant that errors were curbed but not eradicated. This finding agrees with Derwing and Munro's (2015) argument that technology-initiated feedback provides customised and effective pronunciation training, as well as Neri et al.'s (2008) finding that CAPT enhances segmental accuracy by means of repeated, focused input.

Table 5: Summary percentage of Pronunciation Outcomes

Grouping	Participants No	Percentage (%)
Found AI tools useful	40	80
Improved in /θ/	40	80
Improved in /ð/	38	76
Improved in both /θ/ and /ð/	33	66
Reported major challenges	42	84
No significant improvement	17	34

Based on the above findings in the table, ESL students in general found AI feedback to be useful and effective, though they varied in opinion based on the degree of improvement they perceived. Before training through the AI tools, only about 22% of subjects could produce /θ/ correctly in most contexts, and about 18% in the case of /ð/. With some weeks of practice supported by the AI, rates of correct production increased.

According to the results, after the post test, 80% of the participants rated the AI feedback tools as useful for improving pronunciation. Eighty percent (80%) of the learners showed improvement in the voiceless dental fricative /θ/, while 76% improved in the voiced /ð/. About 66% reported significant improvement in both sounds. Regardless of these positive changes, problems like inadequate internet connections, lack of feedback or device breakdowns remained

ENGLISH LANGUAGE TEACHING TODAY(ELTT)

common with 84% of them noting these issues. Approximately 34% did not improve significantly, generally because they did not practice the tools or were unable to use them.

In response to the question concerning their perception of usefulness, 80% of the respondents reported that AI tools, including YouGlish, Forvo, and Praat, provided them with more differentiated auditory models and real-time visual feedback, which allowed them to understand the position of the mouth and airflow to both sounds better. It was especially found to be valued by about 76% to have the opportunity of repeating the listening and practice sessions at their own pace without worrying about being embarrassed. A moderate-sized sample (approximately 15%) indicated moderate satisfaction, noting that while AI helped with individual word practice, it did not work as well for improving spontaneous speech. The remaining 5% were skeptical, thinking their improvement was very slight and that they required more teacher feedback in combination with AI practice.

Several recent studies (Wang et al., 2021; Chen et al., 2019) provide empirical evidence that AI software is capable of enhancing pronunciation accuracy, learner independence, and learner engagement. These findings justify the choice of AI-based feedback as a potential intervention in this study.

Below, in Figure 2, is an example of improvement in the realisation of voiceless dental fricative.

Figure 2: Realisation of Voiceless Dental Fricative /θ/ after AI

In the acoustic analysis of the word "thin in Figure 2," there is a noticeable articulatory change in a comparison between the British speaker's and the Nigerian speaker's pronunciation of the word after a practice of pronunciation teaching.

Following the use of an AI pronunciation tool, however, there is a visible improvement in Nigerian speaker articulation. The resultant spectrogram in Figure 2 shows that there is a total metamorphosis of the original sound. The sound pattern no longer has a silent closure and explosions. Rather, it now has the characteristic of fricatives: a smooth, aperiodic noise. The energy is scattered and dispersed.

The energy is diffuse and spread over a wide frequency range, manifesting on the spectrogram as a blurry, indistinct cloud rather than the precise, fleeting burst of the original try. The important

fact, however, is that the spectrogram lacks the characteristic striation patterns which would be observed if the sound were voiced, confirming the speaker's successful production of the voiceless dental fricative /θ/. Thus, the transition from the first to the second spectrogram is visually established as a successful articulatory adjustment. The Nigerian speaker has moved from allophonic substitution of the dental fricative with a stop consonant to the correct production of the fricative sound, showing evident and obvious improvement in controlling British English phonetics.

Overall, the majority of students perceived AI feedback as an important tool to help improve dental fricative production, with increasing numbers of correct pronunciations providing measurable proof of its worth. Perceptions also indicated that AI was generally of greatest benefit used as an addition to, rather than in place of, human-based pronunciation training.

In response to research question three: What challenges hinder full adoption of such tools?

From the Table 3, the most important hindrance to the full adoption of AI feedback tools is the persistence of pronunciation errors after practice. A substantial majority of the participants — 92% of the females and 88% of the males — still reported having trouble producing /θ/ and /ð/ even if they had used the tools. This shows that while learners enjoy the feedback, they might struggle with the following:

- i. Excessive L1 influence that interferes with distinguishing and mimicking the target sounds accurately.
- ii. Inadequate practice time or sporadic usage of the AI tool.
- iii. Inability to interpret AI feedback, especially when it's highly technical or not described explicitly.
- iv. Heavy dependence on visual or automated feedback without incorporating them into real-life speaking contexts.

Generally, the high frequency of respondents reporting continued difficulty indicates both linguistic and practical limitations on learning the dental fricatives to full mastery through AI alone.

CONCLUSION

The study concludes that Nigerian ESL learners tend to substitute dental fricatives /θ/ and /ð/ with the stops (/t/ and /d/), respectively, a pattern of substitution typical in second language acquisition. The finding supports Jenkins' (2000) observation that learners are likely to substitute distant sounds in the phonetic sense with sounds closer to their first language's phonemic inventory. However, the application of AI-driven pronunciation websites such as YouGlish and Forvo provided improvement, with learners being more aware and having more accurate production of target sounds.

From an Optimality Theory perspective, this performance shift can be accounted for as a constraint re-ranking process: initially, high-ranked markedness constraints against dental fricatives prompted learners to substitute them with less marked stops; post-AI training, faithfulness constraints such as IDENT-MANNER and IDENT-PLACE gained prominence, resulting in more accurate productions. This pragmatic difference is a statement of the

ENGLISH LANGUAGE TEACHING TODAY(ELTT)

proposition of Boersma and Hayes (2001) of acquisition as a pathway of gradual restructuring of constraint hierarchies.

Still, despite all the promises of AI tools, there are still bumps to soar. Mass adoption is not viable due to inaccessibility in the online domain, low technological skill, and infrastructural limits, in line with the warning Levis (2018) offers that technology integration in pronunciation instruction only succeeds with teacher facilitation and institutional infrastructure. Thus, AI tools are as promising as they sound in solving evergreen pronunciation issues in the Nigerian ESL context, their success in the long-run will depend on a balance between technological innovation and human facilitation and larger-scale infrastructural development.

RECOMMENDATIONS

1. Integrate AI tools into regular pronunciation practice: – Instructors can integrate AI-supported feedback tools in ESL lessons, with emphasis on challenging sounds such as /θ/ and /ð/.
2. Combining AI feedback with instructor guidance: – AI tools can be a complement, not a replacement, for human instruction. Teachers can explain error patterns brought out by the AI and provide targeted drills to enable learners to practice.
3. Provide learner training on using AI tool: – Some participants experienced user or technical problems. Orientation sessions of short duration need to be given to ensure that learners are familiar with how to use the tool and interpret its feed.
4. Encourage regular practice: – Improvement was visible more among learners who practiced daily. Institutions need to give special lab hours or practice hours for practicing AI pronunciation.
5. Address individual learner differences: – Since various learners acquired at different rates, teachers should provide customised support, so that feedback and exercises are designed in relation to skills and L1 background.
6. Position pronunciation within overall communication skills: – AI training on /θ/ and /ð/ should be positioned within real-life communicative contexts in order to enable transfer from isolated sound practice into fluent speech.

REFERENCES

- Boersma, P., & Hayes, B. (2001). Empirical tests of the Gradual Learning Algorithm. *Linguistic Inquiry*, 32(1), 45–86. <https://doi.org/10.1162/002438901554586>
- Boersma, P., & Weenink, D. (2024). *Praat: Doing phonetics by computer* [Computer program]. Version 6.4. <https://www.praat.org/>
- Burns, A., & Hill, D. (2013). Teaching speaking in a second language. In B. Tomlinson (Ed.), *Applied linguistics and materials development* (pp. 231–248). Bloomsbury Academic.
- Celce-Murcia, M., Brinton, D. M., & Goodwin, J. M. (2010). *Teaching pronunciation: A course book and reference guide* (2nd ed.). Cambridge University Press.
- Chen, B., Li, M., & Hsu, J. (2020). The role of artificial intelligence in English language teaching: A new perspective. *Modern Language Journal*, 104(2), 351–368.
- Chen, Y., Zhao, Y., & Chen, J. (2019). Investigating the effectiveness of AI-based feedback on EFL learners' speaking performance. *Journal of Educational Technology & Society*, 22(4), 18–30.

- Cruttenden, A. (2008). *Gimson's pronunciation of English*. Routledge.
- Crystal, D. (2003). *English as a global language* (2nd ed.). Cambridge University Press.
- Davis, F. D. (1989). Perceived usefulness, perceived ease of use, and user acceptance of information technology. *MIS Quarterly*, 13(3), 319–340. <https://doi.org/10.2307/249008>
- Derwing, T. M., & Munro, M. J. (2005). Second language accent and pronunciation teaching: A research-based approach. *TESOL Quarterly*, 39(3), 379–397. <https://doi.org/10.2307/3588486>
- Derwing, T. M., & Munro, M. J. (2015). *Pronunciation fundamentals: Evidence-based perspectives for L2 teaching and research*. John Benjamins. <https://doi.org/10.1075/llt.42>
- Flege, J. E. (1995). Second language speech production: An introduction. In W. B. J. Smits (Ed.), *Proceedings of the 1st International Symposium on the Acquisition of Second Language Speech* (pp. 1–14). Utrecht University.
- Godwin-Jones, R. (2019). Pronunciation and Technology: Trends and issues. *Language Learning & Technology*, 23(1), 1–13.
- Godwin-Jones, R. (2021). AI in language learning: A new frontier. *Language Learning & Technology*, 25(1), 1–11.
- Gonet, W., & Pietron, G. (2006). English interdental fricatives in the speech of Polish learners of English. *Dydaktyka Fonetyki Języka Obcego. Neofilologia*, 8, 73–86.
- Gut, U. (2004). *Nigerian English: Phonology*. In B. Kortmann & E. W. Schneider (Eds.), *A handbook of varieties of English: Phonology* (pp. 813–826). Mouton de Gruyter.
- Hassan, A., & Al-Rabeh, F. (2023). Acoustic and perceptual analysis of the effects of AI-powered pronunciation apps on Arabic-speaking EFL learners. *Journal of Applied Linguistics and Language Research*, 10(2), 1–15.
- Horwitz, E. K., Horwitz, M. B., & Cope, J. (1986). Foreign language classroom anxiety. *The Modern Language Journal*, 70(2), 125–132.
- “Interference Theory”. (2013). In *Wikipedia*. Retrieved April 19, 2013, from http://wikipedia/Interference_theory.html
- Jha, A. (2024). *Challenges of learning English as a second language*. Medium. Retrieved July 10, 2025, from <https://medium.com/@jha.ameet/challenges-of-learning-english-as-a-second-language-3533ccf29126>
- Jenkins, J. (2000). *The phonology of English as an international language: New models, new norms, new goals*. Oxford University Press.
- Jolayemi, D. & Adebayo, M. O. (2023). Variation in palato-alveolar fricatives of undergraduates’ spoken English. *International Journal of Research in Education Humanities and Commerce*, 4(2), 205–219.
- Jowitt, D. (1991). *Nigerian English usage: An introduction*. Longman.
- Kurniawan, D. (2016). The error analysis of the pronunciation of dental fricative consonants (/θ/, /ð/) by the students of English education study program faculty of teacher training and education Sriwijaya University. *The Journal of English Literacy Education: The Teaching and Learning of English as a Foreign Language*, 3(2), 157–163.
- Ladefoged, P. (2005). *Vowels and consonants: An introduction to the sounds of languages* (2nd ed.). Blackwell Publishing.
- Levis, J. M. (2018). *Intelligibility, oral communication, and the teaching of pronunciation*. Cambridge University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1017/9781108241564>

ENGLISH LANGUAGE TEACHING TODAY(ELTT)

- Maddieson, I. (2013). *The atlas of languages: The origin and development of languages throughout the world*. Facts On File.
- McCarthy, J. J., & Prince, A. (1993). Generalized alignment. In G. Booij & J. van Marle (Eds.), *Yearbook of Morphology 1993* (pp. 79–153). Springer. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-94-017-3712-8_4
- Mubarok, A. F., Salim, M. A., & Deliany, Z. (2025). AI-based applications to foster pronunciation accuracy. *Essence: Teaching English as a Foreign Language, Linguistics, and Literature Journal*, 2(1), 71–80.
- Mushthoza, D. A., Syariatn, N., Tahalele, O., Telussa, S. I., Rasmita, R., & Mokodenseho, S. (2023). Analyzing the impact of artificial intelligence (AI) on the future of English language teaching and learning. *Journal on Education*, 6(1), 808–815.
- Neri, A., Cucchiari, C., Strik, H., & Boves, L. (2008). The pedagogy–technology interface in computer assisted pronunciation training. *Computer Assisted Language Learning*, 21(5), 441–465. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09588220802447651>
- Owolabi, D. (2012). Production and perception problems of English dental fricatives by Yoruba speakers of English as a second language. *Theory & Practice in Language Studies*, 2(6).
- Prince, A., & Smolensky, P. (1993). *Optimality Theory: Constraint interaction in generative grammar* (Technical Report no. RuCCS-TR-2). New Brunswick, NJ: Rutgers University Center for Cognitive Science.
- Raja, A. (2023). The importance of English in the globalized world. *International Journal of Innovative Research in Technology (IJIRT)*, 9(11), 1214–1218.
- Rosewarne, D., & Basso, R. B. (2018). On English Dental Fricatives. *Ideas*, 3(3).
- Rusmiyanto, R., Huriati, N., Fitriani, N., Tyas, N. K., Rofi'i, A., & Sari, M. N. (2023). The role of artificial intelligence (AI) in developing English language learner's communication skills. *Journal on Education*, 6(1), 750–757.
- Saito, Y. (2011). The effects of instruction and feedback on the learning of English pronunciation. *System*, 39(1), 12–25.
- Szmigiera, M. (2022). *The most spoken languages worldwide in 2022*. Statista. <https://www.statista.com/statistics/266808/the-most-spoken-languages-worldwide/>
- Ugorji, C. U. (2010). Phonological variation in Nigerian English: Implications for international intelligibility. *Journal of Nigerian Languages and Culture*, 12(1), 82–99.
- Wang, Q., Zhang, L., & Li, H. (2021). The impact of AI-based speech recognition on EFL learners' pronunciation accuracy and self-efficacy. *Computer Assisted Language Learning*, 34(6), 845–862.
- Wester, F., Gilbers, D., & Lowie, W. (2007). Substitution of dental fricatives in English by Dutch L2 speakers. *Language Sciences*, 29(2–3), 477–491.
- Xu, H. B. & Ismail, H. H. (2024). The impact of artificial intelligence-assisted learning applications on oral English ability: A literature review. *International Journal of Academic Research in Progressive Education and Development*, 13(4). <http://dx.doi.org/10.6007/IJARPED/v13-i4/23352>